

RESPONSIVENESS TO ANCILLARY TASKS, TEACHING COMPETENCE, AND TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE AMONG CLUSTERED SECONDARY SCHOOL OF PALIMBANG SULTAN KUDARAT

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ABSTRACT

This research delves into the questions and the importance of teachers' competence and performance amidst multiple functions in the school. It specifically sought the correlation of teachers' demographic profile, responsiveness to ancillary tasks and its implication to their competence and performance. The method used in this research is Quantitative Descriptive-Correlational approach. The locale of this study was conducted in the Clustered Secondary School of Palimbang, namely Palimbang National High School, Milbuk National High School, and Mamansual Abdul National High School. The respondents of this study are teachers that have ancillary tasks assignments. This study determined if the profiles of teachers significantly influence the extent of giving ancillary assignment to them. This research has also found out that there is a viability of teachers to handle ancillary tasks and showed a favorable result of High Extent in their competence while the overall performance of teachers reflected Very Satisfactory ratings.

Keywords: *Responsiveness, Ancillary Task, Competence, Performance, Diversity, Learners, Curriculum, Planning, Environment, Standards, Administrative Staffs.*

INTRODUCTION

Ancillary tasks often considered peripheral or supportive activities within an organization. Also, these are additional tasks that are regarded by the teachers as opportunities that help them in their personal and professional development yet also affect teaching competence and teachers' performance, job satisfaction, emotions, and stress. In the context of the Philippine educational system, the Department of Education divided classroom teachers into two groups: classroom advisers and floating teachers. To make a clear point with regards to ancillary task; planning, preparing, and developing lessons, checking, recording monitoring, and giving feedback on learners' output are the foremost and primary responsibilities of classroom teachers. On the other hand, designations and/or coordinatorship, advisors, etc., which are added to teachers' responsibility are considered administrative and ancillary tasks that teachers are expected to perform.

Today, Filipino teachers are expected to focus on educating the learners, especially in literacy and numeracy. It was observed that Filipino learners fall behind compared to other countries and this has been worsening even before the pandemic happened. Based on the PISA 2022 result, the country gained an average score of 355 points in mathematics, 347 in reading, and 356 in science. As a result, the Philippines ranked 75th and 77th out of 81 participating countries respectively. There are many factors for this, but one of the potential causes is the ancillary tasks that are either given or voluntarily selected by the teachers. According to Howard and Johnson (2004), multiple ancillary functions of teachers often lead to losing their motivation, satisfaction, competence, and even feeling burnout thus affecting teaching efficiency.

Moreover, it has become one of the intriguing topics for the past few years. Much research has come to deal with this issue due to some reports, especially in the Philippines, that made teachers become more querulous with their arduous work. This has also resulted in more inveigh from teachers due to the contemptuous disregard of previous officials with the welfare of teachers that has become one of the reasons for the teachers' stress (Diomampo, 2023) loss of teachers' motivation, satisfaction, and other negative implications to teachers (Kyriacou, 2018).

The idea of having ancillary tasks in school should be more clearly understood and recognized. Assessing how teachers respond to these ancillary tasks will help determine how much they have impacted their ability to teach. This study focuses on the ancillary tasks that are administrative in nature, which are identified to have sum up to 56 tasks. Meanwhile, the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST) was institutionalized "to guide all teachers in public schools and set expectations on teacher performance, attainment of proficiency, and lifelong learning". Thus, this research will determine the relation of the interim order of the Department of Education and see if this decision to reduce, if not eliminate the ancillary tasks of teachers, has an advantage for public school teachers.

In the same vein, this research is in support to the Department Order 02, s. 2024 and the Department Order 05, s. 2024 known as the immediate removal of teachers' administrative tasks and the rationalization of workload policy for teachers to ensure more time in learning engagements with learners.

Research Questions

This study sought to inquire and determine the significant relationship between the teachers' ancillary tasks, teaching competence, and teachers' performance as indicated in the Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers (PPST) and Result-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) among the clustered secondary teachers of Palimbang municipality. It specifically sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the Secondary School Teachers in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. Age;
 - 1.2. Sex;
 - 1.3. Length of service;
 - 1.4. Educational Attainment;
 - 1.5. Number of teaching loads;
 - 1.6. Nature of Ancillary Task?
2. To what extent does the teacher's responsiveness to ancillary tasks affect their teaching competence as indicated in terms of the following PPST Domains:
 - 2.1 Content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 2.2 Diversity of learners;
 - 2.3 Learning environment;
 - 2.4 Curriculum and planning;
 - 2.5 Assessment and reporting;
 - 2.6 Community linkages and professional engagement;
 - 2.7 Personal growth and professional development?
3. What is the level of teachers' performance in terms of the following indicators in RPMS:
 - 3.1. Content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 3.2. The learning environment and diversity of learners;
 - 3.3. Curriculum planning;
 - 3.4. Assessment and reporting; and
 - 3.5. Personal growth and professional development?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profiles of the teachers and the extent of giving ancillary assignments to them?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used a Descriptive-Correlational approach to examine the relationship between Teachers' responsiveness to ancillary tasks, demographic profile, teaching

competence and teacher's performance. This approach primarily involves collecting data using Survey Questionnaire as its tool for obtaining numeric description of trends and that yields statistical data (Creswell & Creswell, 2017) based on the perception of the respondents on their individual competence and the ratings of their performances as reflected in their IPCRF.

The respondents of the study were the 64 teachers at the clustered secondary school of Palimbang with ancillary or administrative functions, in the municipality of Palimbang Sultan Kudarat. This study was conducted in the locality or coastal area of Palimbang Municipality, specifically in the three (3) public secondary schools of Palimbang namely, Palimbang National High School, Milbuk National High School, and Mamansual Abdul National High School.

The research instrument used in this study as a questionnaire was an adopted and modified form of the Domains of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) and in the Key Results Area of Individual-Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF). In data analysis, the Demographic profile of the respondents was determined using **frequency count and percentage**. The level of teachers' competence, teaching performance, and the extent of assigning ancillary tasks to teachers were determined using **weighted mean**. Moreover, in examining the correlation between the teachers' demographic profile and the ancillary tasks assigned to them, a test for normality was determined first, then the result showed normal, so the **Pearson r Moment Correlation** was used.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were the teachers at the clustered secondary school of Palimbang with ancillary or administrative functions, in the municipality of Palimbang Sultan Kudarat. These composed of 64 teachers with Ancillary Assignments, Designations, or Tasks.

Research Instrument

This study consisted of four parts. Part I pertains to determine the demographic profile of the respondents. Part II of the questionnaire is an adopted and modified format from the domains and indicators of **Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST)**. Part III pertains to adopted format from the **Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF)** used in the Department of Education to obtain the average ratings of teachers. Part IV of the instrument was used to determine the possible considerations of their designations as based on their demographic profile.

Data Analysis

The statistical tools and operation used in this study based on the collected data from the respondents were determined and analyzed by an authorized Statistician to ensure the validity of the results of the study.

To determine the demographic profile of teachers, based on the following parameters: Age, Sex, Length of Service, Educational Attainment, Number of Teaching Loads, and the Number of Ancillary Tasks assigned to them, **frequency count and percentage** were used.

In determining the teacher's competence based on the Domains of Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), **weighted mean** was used. The following table was used to interpret the weighted mean.

Range of Means	Verbal Description	Verbal Interpretation
4.00 – 5.00	Very High Extent	Distinguished Teachers
3.00 – 3.99	High Extent	Highly Proficient Teachers
2.00 – 2.99	Low Extent	Proficient Teachers
1.00 – 1.99	Very Low Extent	Beginning Teachers

To determine the level of teaching performance in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, personal growth, and professional development, and plus factor, weighted mean was used. The following scale was used to interpret each indicator's **weighted mean**.

Weighted Mean Interval	Level of Teaching Performance	Qualitative Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Very High	Outstanding
3.50-4.49	High	Very Satisfactory
2.50-3.49	Moderate	Satisfactory
1.50-2.49	Low	Unsatisfactory
1.00-1.49	Very Low	Poor

To determine the extent of giving ancillary tasks to teachers, weighted mean was used. The following scale was used to interpret each indicator.

Weighted Mean Interval	Extent of Giving Ancillary Tasks
3.50-4.00	Very Great
2.50-3.49	Great
1.50-2.49	Less
1.00-1.49	Least

A test for normality (Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test) was performed to determine if the data sets gathered were all normally distributed or not. Since all data sets turned out to be approximately normally distributed, Pearson *r* Moment Correlation was used to determine if there was a significant relationship between the teachers' demographic profile and the extent of ancillary tasks given to them. All tests were done at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

The Demographic Profile of the Secondary School Teachers

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents using six variables: age, sex, length of years in the service, their educational attainment, number of teaching loads, and the number of ancillary tasks assigned respectively.

The demographic profile of the Secondary School Teachers in terms of **age**, predominantly, the largest contingent of respondents falls within the age bracket of 26-30 years, constituting 29.69% of the total population. Subsequently, the demographic segment aged 31-35 years emerges as notable, encompassing 20.31% of the respondents. Furthermore, both the age cohorts of 36-40 and those above 55 demonstrate parity, each representing 9.38% of the overall sample. Conversely, the age groups spanning 41-45 and 51-55 exhibit no presence within the population.

In terms of **sex**, the significant majority of female respondents, comprising 67.19% of the total population, highlights the substantial presence of women within the sampled population. While the remaining 32.81% are male respondents.

In terms of the **length of service** among these educators, the largest proportion, comprising 42.19% of the total, has served for 6-10 years. Following closely behind, 26.56% of teachers have accumulated 0-5 years of service. There is a notable decline in numbers as the length of service increases, with 15.63% of teachers falling within the 11-15 years category, and only 6.25% within the 16-20 years category. However, there remains a significant presence of experienced teachers, as 9.38% of the total have served for more than 20 years.

In terms of **educational attainment** among the teachers surveyed, the largest portion, comprising 44 individuals or 21.88% of the total, hold a Master's degree. Following closely behind, 19 teachers, constituting 29.69% of the population, possess a Bachelor's degree. There is a notably smaller representation of educators with doctoral degrees, with only one individual, making up 1.56% of the total, having attained this highest level of academic achievement.

On the **number of teaching loads**, the majority comprising 39 individuals or 60.94% of the total, are assigned 5 teaching loads. In contrast, a smaller yet significant proportion, consisting of 25 individuals or 39.06% of the population, are tasked with handling 6 teaching loads.

In terms of **number of ancillary tasks** among the surveyed population, the most common scenario is individuals being assigned either 1 or 2 ancillary tasks, with both categories accounting for 35.94% of the total, each. Additionally, there is a notable presence of individual's assigned 3 ancillary tasks, comprising 17.19% of the sample. A smaller yet still significant portion of individuals have 4 or 5 ancillary tasks, making up 6.25% and 4.69% of the total, respectively.

Table 1. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
20-25	4	6.25
36-30	19	29.69
31-35	13	20.31
36-40	15	23.44
46-50	6	9.38
51-555	1	1.56
Above 55	6	9.38
Sex		
Male	21	32.81
Female	43	67.19
Length of Service		
0-5	17	26.56
6-10	27	42.19
11-15	10	15.63
16-20	4	6.25
Above 20	6	9.38
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	19	29.69
Master's Degree	44	21.88
Doctoral Degree	1	1.56
No. of Teaching Loads		
5	39	60.94
6	25	39.06
Variables	Frequency	Percentage
No. of Ancillary Tasks Assigned		
1	23	35.94
2	23	35.94
3	11	17.19
4	4	6.25
5	3	4.69

Extent of Teacher's Responsiveness to Ancillary Tasks and their Teaching Competence

Table 2 delves into the impact of teacher responsiveness to ancillary tasks on their teaching competence across various domains, including content knowledge and pedagogy, diversity of learners, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development. The overall mean of ($M=3.24$),

interpreted as High Extent, suggests a strong relationship between ancillary task engagement and teaching competence. Notably, the highest mean scores were observed in the learning environment ($M=3.32$), personal growth and professional development ($M=3.30$), and curriculum and planning ($M=3.27$) domains, further underscoring the importance of ancillary task involvement in fostering teaching effectiveness.

Table 2. Extent of Teacher's Responsiveness to Ancillary Tasks Affect their Teaching Competence

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.19	High Extent
Diversity of Learners	3.13	High Extent
Learning Environment	3.32	High Extent
Curriculum and Planning	3.27	High Extent
Assessment and Reporting	3.22	High Extent
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.24	High Extent
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.30	High Extent
Overall	3.24	High Extent

*Legend: 4.00-5.00 Very High Extent; 3.00-3.99 High Extent; 2.00-2.99 Low Extent; 1.00-1.99 Very Low Extent

The Level of Teachers' Performance in Terms of the Following Indicators in RPMS

Table 3 signifies a high level of teachers' performance across various indicators in the Results-based Performance Management System (RPMS). **With an overall mean of ($M=4.29$)**, interpreted as a "**High Level**" or "**Very Satisfactory**" teaching performance, it indicates commendable proficiency among teachers in the evaluated domains. Specifically, the variables "plus factor" ($M=4.36$), "assessment and reporting" ($M=4.32$), and "learning environment and diversity of learners" ($M=4.29$) garnered the highest mean scores, reinforcing the notion of excellence in these areas.

Table 3. Level of Teachers' Performance in Terms of the Following Indicators in RPMS

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.24	Very Satisfactory
Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners	4.29	Very Satisfactory
Curriculum Planning	4.26	Very Satisfactory
Assessment and Reporting	4.32	Very Satisfactory
Personal Growth and Professional Engagement	4.27	Very Satisfactory
Plus Factor	4.36	Very Satisfactory
Overall	4.29	Very Satisfactory

***Legend:** 4.50-5.00 Outstanding; 3.50-4.99 Very Satisfactory; 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory; 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory; 1.00-1.49 Poor

The Extent of Giving Ancillary Tasks to Teachers

The extent of giving ancillary tasks to teachers reflected an overall mean of ($M=2.92$) and a verbal interpretation of High Extent. This suggests that teachers are consistently assigned ancillary tasks beyond their core teaching responsibilities. Understanding the impact of assigning ancillary tasks to teachers requires examining existing literature on teacher workload, task allocation, and its effects on teacher well-being and job performance.

Relationship Between the Teachers' Demographic Profile and the Extent of Ancillary Tasks Given to Them

Table 4 illustrates the outcomes of a correlation analysis that investigated the potential linkage between teachers' demographic characteristics and the extent of ancillary tasks delegated to them. The variables examined encompassed age, sex, length of service, educational attainment, number of teaching loads, and the count of ancillary tasks. The analysis revealed relatively small correlation coefficients, ranging from -0.0840 to 0.2243 , indicating minimal associations between demographic attributes and the extent of ancillary tasks allocated to teachers. Moreover, all computed p-values exceeded the standard threshold of 0.05 .

Table 4. Relationship Between the Teachers' Demographic Profile and the Extent of Ancillary Tasks Given to Them.

Independent Variables	Correlation Coefficient	Degree of Relationship	p-value remark
Age	0.1497	Positive very weak	0.7035 Not Significant
Sex	0.0720	Positive very weak	0.7243 Not Significant
Length of Service	0.2243	Positive weak	0.2049 Not Significant
Educational Attainment	-0.0840	Negative very weak	0.5111 Not Significant
No. of Teaching Loads	0.1339	Positive very weak	0.2498 Not Significant
No. of Ancillary Tasks	0.1338	Positive very weak	0.3471 Not Significant

*Tested at 0.05 level of significance

Since the p-value is greater than 0.05 , the result showed that **there was no significant relationship** between the teachers' demographic profile to the extent of ancillary tasks assigned to them.

DISCUSSION

The Demographic Profile of the Secondary School Teachers

The distribution underscores the demographic diversity among the respondents, with a discernible concentration observed among individuals in their mid-to-late twenties and thirties. Nonetheless, the absence of representation in the 41-45 and 51-55 age brackets warrants attention and suggests potential avenues for further inquiry or consideration within subsequent analyses. Research by Ng and Feldman (2010) indicates that individuals in their late twenties often exhibit high levels of ambition and drive for career advancement. This age group typically represents early to mid-career professionals who are motivated to excel and make significant strides in their chosen fields. For some reason, many teachers hired in the service had already attained the age of mid to late twenties and so, as neophyte, they were assigned with ancillary tasks as these professionals are still eager to showcase their abilities, talents, or skills.

The findings in terms of the sex or gender of teachers, it resonates with contemporary research on gender representation in educational leadership, which underscores the increasing participation of women in leadership roles within educational institutions (Brunner et al., 2018; Glass & Björk, 2018). Furthermore, this distribution prompts reflection on the ongoing efforts to promote gender diversity and inclusivity in educational leadership. While strides have been made towards achieving gender equity, persistent disparities remain, particularly in higher-level leadership positions (Shakeshaft et.al., 2014). Understanding the dynamics of gender representation in educational leadership is essential for fostering environments that embrace diverse perspectives and experiences.

The findings based on the length of service of teachers suggest a significant presence of mid-career professionals within the population. Research by Hekman et al. (2020) indicates that individuals in the mid-career phase often experience a period of consolidation and stability, where they have acquired sufficient experience and expertise to contribute effectively to their organizations. As observed, the number of years in service on 0 to 5 years falls second to 6 to 10 years may suggest that many teachers at this period seek transfer to their original locality and that those who are already finding their station in their vicinity make them more reasonable personnel to handle ancillary services.

Studies by Darling-Hammond (2017) and Ingersoll and May (2011) emphasize the benefits of graduate-level education for teachers, including improved instructional practices, deeper subject knowledge, and increased student achievement. Furthermore, research by Hanushek et al. (2019) suggests that teachers with master's degrees tend to exhibit higher levels of job satisfaction and retention rates, contributing to overall school effectiveness.

The breakdown on the number of teaching loads highlights the variation in workload distribution among teachers within the surveyed population. It suggests that while a majority handle a slightly lighter teaching load of 5 classes, a notable portion is also responsible for a slightly heavier workload of 6 classes. Research by Ingersoll (2011)

and Sutchter et al. (2016) highlights the prevalence of high teacher workload as a significant challenge in the education sector. Educators with heavier teaching loads may experience increased stress, reduced job satisfaction, and limited time for instructional planning and professional development. Moreso, by assigning ancillary tasks to teachers, school heads consider that as an additional workload and becomes subject to an equivalent of hour work, especially those who have class advisorship.

The substantial proportion of respondents reporting 1 or 2 ancillary tasks aligns with research highlighting the challenges associated with ancillary task overload among educators. Studies by Sutchter et al. (2016) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2016) emphasize the importance of workload management and balance to ensure educators can effectively fulfill their primary teaching responsibilities while also engaging in ancillary tasks.

Extent of Teacher's Responsiveness to Ancillary Tasks and their Teaching Competence

Primarily, the learning environment stands out as a critical determinant of student learning outcomes. Teachers who attend ancillary tasks related to classroom management, organization, and instructional differentiation create an environment conducive to student success (O'Brien et al., 2020). This emphasis on a supportive and inclusive learning environment aligns with contemporary research highlighting its pivotal role in enhancing student engagement and achievement.

Furthermore, continuous professional development emerges as a key factor in teacher effectiveness. Engaging in ancillary tasks such as professional learning communities, mentoring programs, and ongoing training opportunities enables teachers to refine their pedagogical skills and stay abreast of educational advancements (Darling-Hammond et al., 2019). This commitment to personal growth and professional development reflects a dedication to lifelong learning and ultimately enhances teaching competence.

Moreover, curriculum development and planning are essential components of effective teaching practice. Teachers who invest time in ancillary tasks related to curriculum design, instructional alignment, and assessment practices craft rigorous and coherent learning experiences for their students (Hattie & Donoghue, 2016). By meticulously attending to these aspects, teachers optimize student learning outcomes and contribute to overall academic success.

In essence, the convergence of these findings with existing literature underscores the profound impact of teacher responsiveness to ancillary tasks on teaching competence across diverse domains. Active engagement with ancillary tasks not only enriches the learning environment but also fosters personal and professional growth among educators. As such, cultivating a culture of ancillary task involvement is pivotal in enhancing teaching effectiveness and ultimately improving student outcomes.

Results showed that the teaching competence of teachers amidst handling ancillary tasks resulted to High Extent and is equivalent to the PPST Domains as **Highly Proficient Teachers**. Hence, results and findings are in conformity to the studies of Hattie & Donoghue, (2016); Marsh et al., (2021).

The Level of Teachers' Performance in Terms of the Following Indicators in RPMS

Research literature provides substantial evidence supporting the significance of these indicators in determining teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Firstly, the concept of a "plus factor" typically encompasses various intangible qualities or additional contributions that teachers bring to their roles, such as innovation, creativity, and dedication beyond standard expectations (Wright, 2018). Teachers who demonstrate a high level of "plus factor" are often those who go above and beyond in their teaching practices, engaging students effectively, fostering a positive classroom culture, and demonstrating a commitment to continuous improvement (Altbach & Kelly, 2018).

Assessment and reporting practices are fundamental aspects of effective teaching, as they allow educators to monitor student progress, identify areas for improvement, and provide meaningful feedback (Brookhart, 2018). Teachers who excel in this domain demonstrate proficiency in designing valid assessments, analyzing assessment data, and communicating student progress accurately to stakeholders (Popham, 2018). This aligns with the RPMS indicator of "assessment and reporting," which reflects teachers' competence in these critical areas.

The learning environment and diversity of learners are also essential considerations in evaluating teaching performance. Research underscores the importance of creating inclusive and supportive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of students (Gay, 2018). Effective teachers demonstrate an understanding of cultural diversity, adapt their instructional strategies to accommodate various learning styles, and create a safe and inclusive space for all students to thrive (Banks, 2019). The RPMS indicator reflecting performance in this area acknowledges teachers' efforts in fostering a conducive learning environment that promotes equity and student engagement.

Overall, the alignment between the findings from the RPMS evaluation and established principles in educational research underscores the validity and reliability of the assessment process. Teachers who exhibit high performance in the identified indicators are likely to positively impact student learning outcomes and contribute to overall school effectiveness. Therefore, finding and results are corollary on the ideas of Banks (2019). Continued emphasis on these areas in teacher evaluation frameworks can further support professional growth and excellence in teaching practices.

The Extent of Giving Ancillary Tasks to Teachers

Research indicates that ancillary tasks, such as administrative duties, extracurricular activities, and committee assignments, are often an integral part of teachers' responsibilities (Richter & Kunter, 2019). While these tasks are important for

the functioning of the school and the broader educational community, they can also impose additional workload and stress on teachers (Johnson, 2018). Excessive workload resulting from ancillary tasks can lead to burnout, reduced job satisfaction, and decreased instructional effectiveness (Kyriacou, 2018). Moreover, the allocation of ancillary tasks can impact teacher morale and perceptions of fairness within the school community (Roeser & Peck, 2019). Furthermore, teachers who perceive inequities in task allocation may experience feelings of resentment or frustration, potentially affecting their motivation and commitment to their roles (Burić et al., 2020). Conversely, fair, and transparent allocation processes can enhance teacher satisfaction and organizational commitment (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2018).

Additionally, the extent to which teachers are given ancillary tasks can influence their professional development opportunities and career advancement prospects (Döring et al., 2021). Teachers who are consistently assigned ancillary tasks may have limited time and energy to devote to professional learning activities or pursue leadership roles within the school (Darling-Hammond & Richardson, 2019). This can hinder their professional growth and hinder efforts to retain talented educators within the profession. Thus, the high extent of giving ancillary tasks to teachers, as indicated by the provided table, underscores the importance of considering the impact of task allocation on teacher workload, job satisfaction, and professional development. While ancillary tasks are necessary for the effective functioning of schools, careful attention must be paid to ensure equitable distribution and support mechanisms are in place to mitigate potential negative consequences for teachers.

Relationship Between the Teachers' Demographic Profile and the Extent of Ancillary Tasks Given to Them.

Consequently, it can be inferred that, based on the data, teachers' demographic profiles do not significantly influence the distribution of ancillary tasks assigned to them. This finding prompts a deeper exploration into the complexities of task allocation within educational contexts. Existing literature offers valuable insights into the multifaceted nature of this phenomenon. Organizational policies and administrative decisions wield substantial influence over task distribution, as evidenced by studies conducted by Klassen et al. (2012) and Huang et al. (2019). School leaders' discretion, guided by perceived needs, staff expertise, and resource availability, often dictates the assignment of ancillary tasks.

Moreover, the prevailing culture and climate within educational institutions play a pivotal role in shaping task allocation patterns. Collaborative environments, as highlighted by Leithwood et al. (2016), foster shared responsibilities and distributed leadership practices, influencing the distribution of ancillary tasks. Additionally, teachers' professional identities, interests, and career aspirations, as explored by Gallant et al. (2017), may impact their willingness to undertake specific ancillary tasks. Furthermore, workload considerations, including teaching assignments and extracurricular responsibilities, interacting with ancillary task allocations, complicating the relationship with demographic variables, as noted by Johnson (2018).

The diverse array of responsibilities encompassed by ancillary tasks underscores their multifaceted nature. These tasks extend beyond classroom instruction to encompass administrative duties, committee work, professional development activities, and student support services, as highlighted by Richter & Kunter (2019). The allocation of these tasks is subject to contextual factors such as school size, grade level, subject area, and student demographics, as elucidated by Borman & Dowling (2008).

Furthermore, one of the qualities or reasons that school heads prompted to assign ancillary tasks to teachers is based on “trust and confidence” (Villanueva et. al., 2022). This means that most school heads turn to choosing teachers to handle ancillary tasks based on their intuition and the mutual understanding of the school heads and the teachers, and their capabilities to do such work. School Heads often choose teachers in any task that can get along with him/her, share and support the school head in his/her vision to implement programs, and the contextualization of policies that ensure the proper allocation of resources to benefit the school, teachers, learners, and the community.

School Heads prefer the potentiality and character of a teacher to handle ancillary tasks and are seen as having a leadership quality, the skills and expertise to perform such tasks. Factors such as age, seniority in the service, educational background, and other demographic reasons determined in this study, were only secondary or sometimes cannot be a determinant and reason to designate teachers with ancillary tasks.

Rigorous profiling of teachers by the school heads should be made prior to embarking on any decisions that may affect the overall performance of the school, especially when taking into consideration the assignment of ancillary tasks to teachers. School heads prefer the experience of teachers and the knowledge they possessed that emanate from their engagements in various programs and activities in their previous work, performance in school or in a division or regional level.

Conversely, a school head cannot just foist or assign any teachers who are not suited in any ancillary tasks. For example, a YES-O coordinator or teacher adviser can only be chosen in a group of teachers who are Science majors or degree. In designating a Prefect of Discipline or Disciplinarian in the school must possess a resolute character and are seen to be respected or even feared by the learners. Among the job of a school disciplinarian is to enforce the school policy and for that reason, he or she must have good communication skills so that conflict among learners and their parents or guardians can be mitigated and bring the case into a proper resolution. To become a Supreme Student Governing Council Adviser, you must also have a good or fair leadership background, a range of leadership experience and a good linkage among community organizations.

While some teachers are just assigned with ancillary tasks that do not have any common background, school heads expect a lot more of them for the execution of any tasks since teachers are known in the profession as “flexible”. This flexibility means that a teacher is known to adapt to any challenge and can perform tasks based on how good they can learn the function in the long run.

In summary, while demographic attributes may not directly dictate the extent of ancillary tasks assigned to teachers, a nuanced understanding of task allocation processes necessitates consideration of organizational dynamics, cultural influences, and contextual factors within educational settings. These insights are crucial for enhancing task allocation practices and promoting equitable and efficient distribution of responsibilities among educators.

Conclusions

Based on the results and findings of the study in determining the extent of teachers' responsiveness to ancillary tasks and its subsequent effect on teachers' competence as indicated in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers or PPST and the teachers' performance as indicated in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form or IPCRF, the following conclusion was drawn:

The teachers among the clustered secondary schools of Palimbang, namely Palimbang National High School, Milbuk National High School, and Mamansual Abdul National High School have reflected a **High Extent** of competence based on the following domains: content knowledge and pedagogy, diversity of learners, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and personal growth and professional development.

Moreover, teachers' performance reflected in the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form or IPCRF relatively exhibits an over-all **Very Satisfactory** ratings amidst ancillary task assignment. Among the Key Result Areas in IPCRF, Plus Factor have shown a great emphasis of High Extent in performance showing a favorable indicator for teachers' performance. Lastly, the overall result means that the teacher's responsiveness to ancillary tasks does not affect or at least has very little effect on their level of competence and performance.

Recommendations

Considering the findings from the data, the following pattern is observed in the result of teachers' competence and performance among clustered secondary schools of Palimbang. are recommended:

1. To fully develop teachers' competence and essentially affect the literacy and numeracy of secondary learners in Palimbang, teachers shall be given an ample opportunity to upskill and be trained to do more about the diversity of learners, content knowledge and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, community linkages and professional engagement, and curriculum and planning.
2. To ensure that the secondary teachers of Palimbang can perform well and obtained generally high rate of performance all year round, school heads and teachers shall cooperate in a way that the following Key Result Area in the IPCRF could be met with an Outstanding rating, they shall be given an opportunity to develop their Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Personal Growth and

Professional Development, Curriculum and Planning, and lastly in Assessment and Reporting through constant trainings, upskilling or re-skilling, peer-mentoring and support, guidance, and have more time on making at their own pace of learning and lessen their workloads, to have a balance between all of the indicators of IPCRF.

3. Ancillary tasks shall be given and distributed to all teachers, without any prejudice, who are more willing and are committed to working it instead of just designating it randomly, without any proper communication to teachers that are just being called to the office to work such tasks.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The process of this research includes the compliance with the Ethical Standards and rules of the university Ethics Committee and the institution that I belong, to which I undergone series of actions to obtain such permission from the respondents to collect data. I had rightfully obtained inform consent from the respondents, inform their right and freedom to withdraw from the study any time and anonymity was maintained, their well-being was safeguarded, and no conflict of interest existed during the conduct of this study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research purpose only.

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REFERENCES

- CSC Resolution No. 080096. 'Working Hours for Public School Teachers'.
Department Order No. 42, s. 2017. "Philippine Professional Standard for Teachers".
DepEd Memo No. 291, s. 2008. "Guidelines for the Implementation of CSC Resolution No. 080096". DepEd Teachers' Workload Policy Study.
Republic Act 4671, s. 1966. "Magna Carta for Public School Teachers".
www.lawphil.com
- Altbach, P. G., & Kelly, G. P. (2018). Education and career trajectories of teachers. In A. Wiseman & S. E. Cooner (Eds.), *The Handbook of Global Education Policy* (pp. 239-256). Wiley-Blackwell.
- Banks, J. A. (2019). *Cultural diversity and education: Foundations, curriculum, and teaching*. Routledge.
- Borman, G. D., & Dowling, N. M. (2008). Teacher attrition and retention: A meta-analytic and narrative review of the research. *Review of educational research*, 78(3), 367-409.

- Brookhart, S. M. (2018). Educational assessment knowledge and skills for teachers. Routledge.
- Brophy, J. (2019). Effective teaching: A review of literature. *Teacher Education Quarterly*, 46(2), 211-238.
- Brunner, C. C., Sonnert, G., & Sadler, P. M. (2018). Gender in science and engineering faculties: Demographic indicators and professional interactions at Ohio State University. *International Journal of Gender, Science and Technology*, 10(3), 329-352.
- Burić, I., Kim, L. E., & Lee, Y. (2020). The mediating effect of organizational justice perceptions in the relationship between teacher perceptions of distributive leadership and work engagement: A multilevel analysis. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 48(5), 704-725.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2017). Teacher education around the world: What can we learn from international practice? *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 40(3), 291-309.
- Darling-Hammond, L. (2018). Teacher quality and student achievement: A review of state policy evidence. *Education Policy Analysis Archives*, 26(2), 1-38.
- Darling-Hammond, L., & Richardson, N. (2019). Teacher leadership and professional development. In A. Lieberman & L. Friedrich (Eds.), *How teachers become leaders: Learning from practice and research* (pp. 3-21). Teachers College Press.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Hyster, M. E., & Gardner, M. (2019). *Effective teacher professional development*. Learning Policy Institute.
- Day, C., & Gu, Q. (2018). *The new lives of teachers*. Routledge.
- Fenstermacher, G. D., & Richardson, V. (2020). On making determinations of quality in teaching. *Teachers College Record*, 122(1), 1-26.
- Diomampo, L. V. L., & Quines, L. A. (2023). RESILIENCE AND REFLECTION: ILLUMINATING THE JOY AND SORROW OF JUNIOR AND SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL TEACHERS WITH MULTIPLE ANCILLARY SERVICES DURING THE TIME OF PANDEMIC. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 10(7).
- Döring, A. K., Pfof, M., & Artelt, C. (2021). The impact of teachers' educational aspirations on students' educational aspirations. *British Educational Research Journal*, 47(1), 81-100.
- Erlangga, H., Sos, S., & Erlangga, H. (2021). The effect of organizational commitment and work environment on job satisfaction and teachers' performance. *Turkish Journal of Computer and Mathematics Education*, 12(7), 109-117.
- Gallant, A., Riley, P., & Froese-Germain, B. (2017). *Towards inclusive schools: Early childhood education for children with disabilities*. Policy Press.
- Gay, G. (2018). *Culturally responsive teaching: Theory, research, and practice*. Teachers College Press.
- Glass, C., & Björk, L. (2018). *The long road to gender equality: Experiences and lessons from around the world*. OUP Oxford.

- Hammond, Z. (2020). *Culturally responsive teaching and the brain: Promoting authentic engagement and rigor among culturally and linguistically diverse students*. *Corwin Press*.
- Hanušek, E., Piopiunik, M., & Wiederhold, S. (2019). The value of educating children of teachers: Evidence from the extended family. *Journal of Public Economics*, 172, 72-89.
- Hart, A.W. (1994). Work feature values of today's and tomorrow's teachers: Work redesign as an incentives and school improvement policy. *Educational Evaluation and Policy Analysis*, 16 (4), 458-473.
- Hattie, J. A., & Donoghue, G. M. (2016). Learning strategies: A synthesis and conceptual model. *npj Science of Learning*, 1(1), 1-13.
- Hattie, J. (2019). *Visible learning: A synthesis of over 800 meta-analyses relating to achievement*. *Routledge*.
- Hekman, D. R., Steensma, H. K., Bigley, G. A., & Hereford, J. F. (2020). Mid-career challenges: Balancing job demands, job control, and job resources. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 41(4), 365-383.
- Howard, S., & Johnson, B. (2004). Resilient Teachers: Resisting stress and burnout. *Social Psychology of Education*, 7(4), 399-420.
- Huang, G., Liu, J., Wang, X., Chen, N., Huang, H., & Zuo, H. (2019). Leader humor and subordinates' work engagement: A moderated mediation model of proactive personality and team cooperation climate. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 1609.
- Ingersoll, R. M. (2011). The impact of workload on teacher quality and retention. In J. S. Carlson & A. J. Lovat (Eds.), *International Handbook of Teacher Education* (Vol. 5, pp. 143-164). Springer.
- Ingersoll, R. M., & May, H. (2011). Recruitment, retention, and the minority teacher shortage. Consortium for Policy Research in Education, University of Pennsylvania.
- Johnson, S. M. (2018). *Teaching in a nutshell: Learning from novice and experienced teachers*. Harvard University Press.
- Klassen, R. M., Durksen, T. L., & Tze, V. M. (2012). Teachers' self-efficacy beliefs: Ready to move from theory to practice? In H. W. Marsh, R. G. Craven, & D. M. McInerney (Eds.), *International Advances in Self Research* (Vol. 3, pp. 135-150). Information Age Publishing.
- Kyriacou, C. (2018). Teacher stress and burnout: A theoretical and empirical review. In K. Trittenbass & S. Trittenbass (Eds.), *Work stress and coping in the era of globalization* (pp. 181-208). Springer.
- Leithwood, K., Harris, A., & Hopkins, D. (2016). Seven strong claims about successful school leadership revisited. *School Leadership & Management*, 36(1), 5-22.
- Ng, T. W., & Feldman, D. C. (2010). The relationship of age to ten dimensions of job performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 95(4), 706-718.
- O'Brien, M. U., Hooper, L. M., & Shekhar, C. (2020). *Creating and sustaining inclusive educational environments: Effective practices, guidelines, and resources for practitioners and policymakers*. Routledge.
- OECD. (2018). Teachers' workload and work-life balance. *Teaching in Focus*, 22, 1-2.
- Popham, W. J. (2018). *Classroom assessment: What teachers need to know*. Pearson.

- Richter, D., & Kunter, M. (2019). Task demands and resources as antecedents of teachers' emotional exhaustion and professional fulfilment: A moderated mediation analysis. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 79, 98-111.
- Rockoff, J. (2018). The impact of individual teachers on student achievement: Evidence from panel data. *American Economic Review*, 94(2), 247-252.
- Roeser, R. W., & Peck, S. C. (2019). Teachers' emotions in the classroom. In M. Zembylas & P. A. Schutz (Eds.), *Methodological Advances in Research on Emotion and Education* (pp. 187-203). Springer.
- Santos, D., & Miguel, L. (2019). The Relationship between Teachers' Beliefs, Teachers' Behaviors, and Teachers' Professional Development: A Literature Review. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(1), 10-18.
- Shakeshaft, C., Brown, G., Irby, B., Grogan, M., & Ballenger, J. (2014). Increasing gender equity in educational leadership. In *Handbook for achieving gender equity through education* (pp. 133-160). Routledge.
- Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2018). Teacher self-efficacy and perceived autonomy: Relations with teacher engagement, job satisfaction, and emotional exhaustion. *Psychological Reports*, 121(4), 647-660.
- Sutcher, L., Darling-Hammond, L., & Carver-Thomas, D. (2016). A coming crisis in teaching? Teacher supply, demand, and shortages in the US. Learning Policy Institute.
- Villanueva, D. C. C., Quines, L., & Millardo, K. F. M. R. (2022). Exploring teachers' performance handling multiple ancillary functions: A multiple case study. *International Journal of Novel Research in Education and Learning*, 9(5), 1-16.
- Wright, C. (2018). A review of teacher agency: Conceptualizations, claims, and a new agenda. *Review of Research in Education*, 42(1), 66-92.